

In my future shoes: using VR decision support tools in moral and practical prenatal decisions for an enriched and less biased simulation of one's future self

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Abstract

Some decisions in pregnancy are difficult to make, and cannot be solved by applying the rational choice model of decision-making as they are morally laden and/or involve the individual's moral and non-moral values. We term these decisions *moral* and *practical prenatal decisions* respectively. An

individual usually engages in *mental simulation* to explore and make these decisions, which tend to be unfamiliar and relatively novel. At the same time, mental simulation is prone to cognitive biases that risk influencing the individual such that a decision of poor decisional quality is made. In this contribution, we contend that the quality of moral and practical prenatal decisions can be improved by providing prospective parents with a virtual reality (VR) tool that supports decision-making by enhancing the process of mental simulation and presenting pertinent information valued by future parents. We will first explore the types of decisions and the identity issues involved in decision-making in pregnancy. We will then identify the limits of contemporary medical decision-making in pregnancy-related choices and examine the possible biases of mental simulation when employed in moral and practical prenatal decisions. Next, we will present the use of VR, its potential as a decision-aid in moral and practical prenatal decisions, and the ethical issues that may arise from its use in these decisions. We follow this by offering practical considerations and recommendations for developing a VR-based decision-aid, and illustrate its implementation using the example of prenatal testing.

Keywords

VR, Virtual Reality, mental simulation, Prenatal testing, decision support tool, decision aid, future self, NIPT, hypothetical decision-making

1. Introduction

There are numerous decisions to be made during a pregnancy. These range from relatively simple health-related decisions to more complex ones that are morally laden and/or require the individual to reflect on the decision while considering the competing values of the multiple roles that she may play in life. We term these complex decisions *moral* and *practical prenatal decisions* respectively.

Rational choice theory – which is often employed in health-related decisions – cannot support individuals in making moral and practical prenatal decisions as it neither accounts for the complexities of such decisions, nor takes into account the transformational nature of the pregnancy experience. This makes the value (taken here to mean the utility or worth) of the available options (i.e. the option value) in these decisions difficult to assess and subject to change. Individuals try to assess the option value of these decisions through mental simulation, which consists of mentally representing oneself choosing an option and its effects. Individuals adopt mental simulation in decisional contexts that are novel and unfamiliar,

such as moral and practical prenatal decisions. However, mental simulation is prone to biases and inaccuracies that may hinder rather than support an individual's decision-making, resulting in decisions of poor decisional quality. Decisional quality refers to the extent to which patients choose and/or receive health care interventions that are congruent with their informed and considered values ('International Patient Decision Aids Standards (IPDAS) Collaboration' 2020; Kennedy 2003).

In this contribution, we respond to the increasing appreciation for facilitating consideration of an individual's values and beliefs in pregnancy-related decisions, and to the individual's need for support in contextualizing the available choices to their personal circumstances. Our aim is to show how the quality of moral and practical prenatal decisions can be improved using virtual reality, a type of immersive technology, which enhances an individual's mental simulation.

In this article, we first explore the types of decisions and identity issues involved in pregnancy, identify the limits of contemporary medical decision-making in pregnancy-related choices and examine the possible biases of mental simulation when employed in moral and practical prenatal decisions. Next, we present the use of VR and its potential as a decision-aid in moral and practical prenatal decisions, and the ethical issues that arise from its employment. We follow this by offering practical considerations and recommendations for developing a VR-based decision-aid, and illustrate its implementation using the example of prenatal testing.

2. Types of decisions and personal identity involved in pregnancy

During pregnancy, an expectant mother faces three different types of decisions of varying degrees of complexity. Many decisions to be made in pregnancy are straightforward and tackled with the same approach as that used in other health states: the rational choice model of decision-making. We call these kind of decisions *ordinary prenatal* ones since they concern routine prenatal care, which is based on medical evidence and systematically put together into clinical guidelines that determine best practice. Making a treatment decision for anaemia in pregnancy is a clear example of an ordinary prenatal decision. The choice between oral iron tablets, iron infusions or blood transfusions tends to be based on the severity of the anaemia, its underlying cause, and its impact on both the mother and her foetus. The woman's healthcare provider would explain the condition, its likely consequences, the risk and benefits of the various treatment options, and the option of non-treatment. Together, the prospective mother and the healthcare provider come to a presumably rational decision based on both the information at hand and the mother's values and preferences, in a process called *shared decision-making*. Other health issues during pregnancy that are approached using the same decision-making model include Rh incompatibility, gestational diabetes, pre-eclampsia, and thyroid issues.

The second kind of decision that prospective mothers face in pregnancy is the morally laden decision, which involves one or more moral values. The moral values at stake in such kinds of decisions are often conflicting, resulting in this kind of decision being more contentious. Easily recognizable decisions that fall into this category include decisions about prenatal testing for disabilities, and abortions. In the case of an abortion for a 'foetal anomaly', a woman's right to bodily autonomy may conflict with disability rights and the rights of a vulnerable subject to come into existence (with reference to the selective abortion of an affected foetus). These value conflicts are made more challenging as their consideration entails considering the controversial issues of defining the beginning of human life and personhood. We call these morally laden decisions *moral prenatal* decisions. Unlike ordinary prenatal decisions, moral prenatal decisions cannot be tackled simply by consulting medical evidence. Instead, they require the employment of the mother's system of moral values, which forms the backbone of her *moral identity*, and which in turn is part of her *practical identity*. As every individual has her own system of moral values, every prospective mother can be expected to respond in a different way to moral prenatal decisions. Practical identity here refers to the specific constellation of values, beliefs, commitments and plans that cause an individual to be that specific individual, and that are expressed in her deliberate actions, i.e. in the practical sphere. Practical identity is the point of view from which an individual reflects and for which she acts, and is constituted by the roles which she identifies with (e.g. a woman, a mother, a partner, a lawyer, etc.) (Korsgaard 1996). These roles represent descriptions under which an individual values herself, finds her life worth living, and her actions worth undertaking (Korsgaard 1996, 101). Moral identity is a subset of practical identity, embracing the individual's moral values, duties, models of behaviour, and ideals of life.

The last type of decisions in pregnancy is similar to moral prenatal decisions, in that it involves the prospective mother's identity and may be contentious. However, these decisions differ from moral prenatal ones in that they involve the individual's practical identity as a whole, which includes both moral and non-moral values. We call these type of decisions *practical prenatal ones*. Practical prenatal decisions require a prospective mother to reflect on decisions from the perspectives of her different roles in life. She has to consider what she wants and what to take care of not only as a moral agent, but also as a citizen, partner, mother, and any other role she might play. It can be expected that practical prenatal decisions largely involve a woman's identity as a mother, i.e. her own idea of what constitutes being a mother, and the duties and tasks related to this role. An example of practical prenatal decisions is the choice between having a natural birth without any pharmacologically mediated pain control, and a medically augmented birthing process (either with pain medications or by an operative delivery). In this case, the woman would have to reflect on the significance of the birthing process to herself – for example, on questions such as whether bearing labour pains is her responsibility as a mother, or whether the natural birthing process is a fundamental experience in becoming a mother.

Moral and practical prenatal decisions are intrinsically difficult decisions to make in part because they involve a woman's moral and practical identities respectively, and in part because pregnancy (and parenthood) are *transformative experiences* that fundamentally alter these very identities. A transformative experience is an event that changes a person's identity, values and preferences (Paul 2014, 17, 94). They can either be *epistemically* transformative or *personally* transformative. An epistemically transformative experience is one in which knowledge that would otherwise remain inaccessible is acquired, with the acquisition of such knowledge dependent on having lived through the experience. A personally transformative experience is one that fundamentally alters one's beliefs, preferences or sense of self. Pregnancy and parenthood can be considered both epistemically and personally transformative. Even if it was possible to access general knowledge about pregnancy and parenthood, there may be unexpected differences in reality when these processes are experienced by a specific individual. Transformative experiences make it difficult for the individual to choose among options since she is unable to attribute a value (in the sense of worth or utility) to them in the present and/or may attribute a different value to them in the future. This makes the application of the rational choice model to a transformative experience challenging, as we will see in the next section.

3. Contemporary Medical Decision-Making in Pregnancy Decisions and its Limits

Rational choice theory is a framework for modelling human behaviour that stems from neo-classical economics. According to the rational choice model, the decision-maker makes a cost-benefit analysis of the available options in relation to her own preferences, constraints, and subjective probability, before making a decision that is the most advantageous and satisfactory to her (Von Neumann and Morgenstern 1944).

Rational decision-making is firmly embedded in the medical decision-making encounter and is inherently part of the process of informed consent, in which patients and healthcare staff discuss the merits and disadvantages of relevant health care options before making a treatment decision. In general, the standard approach of medical decision-making views pregnancy in terms of discrete moments in a very limited period – from conception to the end of gestation (Kukla 2008) – in which the rational choice model is employed. In what follows, we will show that applying the rational choice model to moral and practical prenatal decisions raises several issues.

The typical value assumption of rational choice theory is that individuals are motivated to attain private and instrumental goods that are exchangeable for other non-instrumental goods (Hechter 1994),

such as the individual's values that constitute her practical and moral identity. By applying this value assumption to the medical setting, a physician may assume that maximizing physical health (i.e. an instrumental good) is a priority for patients, as this facilitates the procurement of other goods that lead to living a fulfilling life (Duncan 2010). However, there may be occasions when patients' considerations of non-instrumental goods override considerations of instrumental ones in determining decision outcomes, thus upsetting expectations based on instrumental rationality. Parents may have a particular view on their reverence for life, circumstances may have made the pregnancy a particularly special one, or they may have a different take on what constitutes a life worth living than the medical model might presuppose. An example of the pre-eminence of non-instrumental values over instrumental ones comes from Alison Piepmeier's qualitative study into the decision-making processes of women given a diagnosis of a genetic anomaly on prenatal screening (Piepmeier 2015). The women were confronted with the decision to terminate or continue their pregnancies. Piepmeier describes two mothers, who were both disabled and sexually abused (raped) earlier in their lives, and who were told that the child they were pregnant with would have Down Syndrome. Acutely aware of the vulnerabilities of being a person with a disability, the two women considered what was in the best interest of their child. One mother decided to terminate her pregnancy as a selfless act of protection and love. Conversely, the other continued her pregnancy, worrying that she was being selfish by keeping her child and unsure that she could adequately protect it from the harsh realities of life. Piepmeier's descriptions of the women's assessment of the choice options prior to the decision shows that they did not only consider factors such as the direct health-related quality of life benefits and disadvantages that are included in a process of decision-making grounded on rational choice.

The application of rational choice theory to decision-making is further challenged by the transformative nature of pregnancy and parenthood, as this fundamentally alters one's identity and thus makes it difficult for an individual to predict her preferences for a given option. This questions the basic assumption of the rational choice model, which assumes the individual's capacity to attribute utility to the available options.

On top of this, the application of rational choice theory to moral and practical prenatal decisions is hindered by the gap between the cognitive abilities of the agent of the rational choice theory and those of the actual individual with regards to uncertain outcomes. The actual individual is limited in her ability to represent and compute probabilities and challenged to contextualize population-based statistics to her individual circumstances (Grossi 2005). For instance, a population-based statistic such as the relatively

small 2% chance of conceiving a disabled child is perceived as a 50/50 chance by the prospective mother, since from her first-person perspective, she might either have a disabled child or not (Tymstra 1989).¹

In summary, the rational choice model is insufficient in accounting for the complexities of moral and practical prenatal decisions because it does not take the individual's practical identity into account, does not consider the value she places on non-instrumental goods in the decision, overestimates her ability to compute probabilities and manage uncertain outcomes, and is not applicable to transformative experiences such as pregnancy.

There are two discernible strategies to improve decision-making in moral and practical prenatal decisions. The first consists of an approach that takes into consideration the patient's practical identity and her evaluation of non-instrumental goods by directly involving her in the decision process. This strategy is termed *shared decision-making* and recognizes that the medical knowledge possessed by clinicians needs to be contextualized by the individual, whose personal knowledge allows her to deduce how the various treatment options and its impact on her health could affect her well-being. Both types of knowledge are required to provide effective care resulting in the health-status improvements valued by the patient (Hurley, Birch, and Eyles 1995). While it is easy to understand the necessity of this information-sharing on both sides, it is not clear what the optimal informational needs of both parties are (Charles, Gafni, and Whelan 1997) the necessary information could be expected to vary depending on the circumstances and the individuals involved. What is clear, however, is that in making recommendations of care plans, it is essential that healthcare providers elicit and appreciate the values and preferences of a given patient. In other words, healthcare providers should appreciate their patient's practical identity in facilitating the decision-making process. We will not elaborate further on shared decision-making, as this not the focus of our contribution. Instead, we will focus on an alternative strategy to improve decision-making in moral and practical prenatal decisions: using virtual reality as a decision support tool to elicit a person's practical identity, evaluate and select options in relation to this practical identity, and enhance her ability to mentally simulate alternative courses of action. We will examine mental simulation in relation to decision-making in the next section and investigate the feasibility and potential of virtual reality as a decision-support tool in sections 5 to 7.

¹ The individual is also limited in her ability to mentally simulate the consequences of her actions and her future emotional states. This does not represent an objection to the model of agent of the rational choice theory, as the latter does not make any assumptions regarding the agent's ability of mental simulation. As mental simulation is largely employed by individuals in prenatal decision-making, we will deal with it and its limits in the next section.

4. The individual's forecasting biases in moral and practical prenatal decisions

Mental simulation is one of the main cognitive processes employed by individuals when making unfamiliar and relatively novel choices such as moral and practical prenatal decisions. Mental simulation involves the cognitive construction of hypothetical scenarios or the reconstruction of real scenarios (Taylor and Schneider 1989) by combining episodic and semantic memories with incoming information (e.g. the decisional options) (Shanton and Goldman 2010; Suddendorf and Corballis 2007; Gilbert and Wilson 2007). Mental simulation enables decision-makers to assess the utility of the available options by hypothetically constructing experiences, their corresponding emotive reactions, and their consequences. However, this process is prone to cognitive biases. Cognitive biases are the constraints and limitations on a person's ability to process information and reason, resulting in sub-optimal choices (Kahneman, Slovic, and Tversky 1982; Kahneman and Tversky 1984; Evans 2007).² In the following, we will explore the biases that reduce the accuracy of mental simulation, and that consequently increase the likelihood of making sub-optimal moral or practical prenatal decisions. We will then show how this can be limited by the use of virtual reality (section 6).

The main cause of bias in mental simulation is caused by limitations of *affective forecasting*. Affective forecasting is a form of pre-experience in which the individual predicts her future feelings and emotions (Wilson and Gilbert 2005; Gilbert and Wilson 2007). People are good at predicting the effects of a future event on their emotional state, but not at forecasting the intensity and duration of this future state, i.e. they misrepresent how much pleasure or displeasure an event will bring them and for how long an emotional state will last (Wilson and Gilbert 2005). The most common misrepresentation of a future event occurs because of an overestimation of the intensity and duration of one's own emotional states in the imagined future. This type of misrepresentation is called *impact bias* (Wilson and Gilbert 2005). For example, women waiting for a pregnancy test tend to overestimate their unhappiness at receiving a negative result (Mellers and McGraw 2001).

Mental simulation of one's own future states tends to be more accurate when the contextual factors affecting oneself in the present and in the future are similar, and when the simulation and the future event exert the same influence on the individual's hedonic response and that of her future self. Since contextual factors are often different at different periods of time (e.g. because of the fluctuation of hormonal states causing morning sickness or a state of wellness), the future event and its simulation exert different influences on the individual, and their affective forecast is often inaccurate (Wilson and Gilbert 2003; 2005; Gilbert and Wilson 2007; Kahneman and Tversky 1984). An example of this inaccuracy in

² In this contribution, we are not interested in the mathematical definition of sub-optimality. We roughly define as "sub-optimal" a choice with which the individual is not satisfied and that has negative consequences on her well-being.

affective forecasting is in prospective mothers' underestimation of the degree to which their lives would be transformed by pregnancy and parenthood, even though they were expecting this change (Staneva and Wittkowski 2013).

The difference in contextual factors between the future event and the simulated event bring about an *empathy gap* of 'hot' and 'cold' states in the individual (Loewenstein 1996; Loewenstein, Prelec, and Shatto 1998; Loewenstein and Lerner 2003a). The individual is in a *hot state* when she experiences a strong visceral factor,³ and conversely in a *cold state* when she does not. The empathy gap refers to the tendency of individuals in one state to misrepresent how they would behave in another state. In mental simulations of moral and practical prenatal decisions, this misrepresentation occurs when the prospective mother assumes that her future self would be in a similar state as that of her present self. This empathy gap may influence a woman to favour a natural, drug-free birth over the option of a hospital birth with pharmacological means of pain-management (such as an epidural) when she is in a state of comfort and painlessness. Her present state of comfort and painlessness may induce her to have romanticised expectations of childbirth, and cause her to overestimate her capacity to tolerate pain (Beaton and Gupton 1990; Fenwick, Holloway, and Alexander 2009).

Apart from the mismatch between an individual's present contextual factors and that of her future self, three other biases of mental simulation have been identified (Gilbert and Wilson 2007). Firstly, simulations tend to be constructed based on memorable events that are often unusual, emotional laden and recent, and which may consequently not be the most representative or appropriate for simulating the future event. Secondly, simulations are essentialized, in the sense that they reproduce only the essential features of an event while neglecting mundane details. In the absence of these details, the essential positive and negative aspects of the experience are amplified, distorting the resulting simulation. Thirdly, simulations tend to only partially reproduce events, focusing primarily on the early moments (i.e. an individual's immediate reaction to an event) and omitting the rest of the experience. The omission of the remaining experience does not take into account the adaptation of the individual to the event, resulting in impact bias.

In addition to this, an object (referring here to an event, person, or process) in a mental simulation can be represented at different construal levels. A *high-level construal* of a mentally simulated object is an abstract representation of only its essential and enduring characteristics (e.g. the action of climbing up a mountain), while a *low-level construal* is a more concrete representation, depicting the incidental and more detailed characteristics of the object (e.g. the smell and uneven surface of the rock that one imagines climbing) (Trope and Liberman 2010). A high-level construal representation does not necessarily represent the object inaccurately. It does, however, frame the object in an abstract way that selectively

³ Visceral factors are emotions (e.g. anger, fear), drive states (e.g. hunger, thirst), and feeling states (e.g. pain, pleasure) that motivate people to engage in specific behaviours (Loewenstein 2000).

emphasizes certain aspects of the object and subsequently exerts an influence on the decision-maker (Kahneman and Tversky 1984; Thaler and Sunstein 2008).⁴ An individual's *psychological distance*, referring to the subjective experience of distance between an object and her present self, influences the construal level of the object (Trope and Liberman 2010). The more distant the object is, the higher the construal level it tends to be represented at. The psychological distance of an object and its corresponding construal level during a mental simulation is relevant to pregnancy and parenthood, as moral and practical prenatal decisions are novel and involve future objects (e.g. consequences of actions, the mother's future self, her child) and tend to be represented at a high-level construal (Förster, Liberman, and Shapira 2009; Trope and Liberman 2003). For instance, a woman anticipating motherhood might imagine with ease the essential features of raising her child, such as the intimate bond that she may develop with her child through breastfeeding. However, the tedious routines which are also integral parts of breastfeeding tend to be disregarded in her conceptualization of the breastfeeding process (for example, frustration with latching, sleepless nights, tedious pumping routines and painful engorgements). The decontextualization of objects in high-construal modes triggers a milder emotional reaction, impeding accurate affective forecasting on the part of the mother. Her temporally-distant future self is represented at a high-level construal, with the abstract features of her fixed and dispositional traits predominantly emerging from the simulation, leaving out essential concrete features of her visceral factors. This is further confounded by the transformative nature of these experiences, which make conceiving the future self problematic.

Representing the future self in an abstract manner inclines decision-makers towards treating their future self as a separate person from themselves, resulting in a tendency to treat their present selves preferentially and making short-sighted decisions (Pronin, Olivola, and Kennedy 2008). An example of this attitude toward the future self as applied to practical prenatal decisions is when a woman in her present state disagrees with an episiotomy recommended by her healthcare provider (because of her discomfort with surgical incisions and/or her preference to give birth as naturally as possible), although this may result in deep perineal tears that can themselves be painful, heal poorly, and affect faecal continence in her future self.

The biases of mental simulation can be reduced by increasing the vividness of the simulation and facilitating low-level representations of objects. Hershfield et al. (Hershfield et al. 2011) immersed research participants in a VR environment with an age-progressed avatar and compared their financial behaviours with controls immersed with an avatar of their present selves. Participants using the aged-progressed avatars saved more money for retirement – a proxy for the care of their future selves – compared to the control group. In addition to facilitating more complete representations of objects, the

⁴ For instance, in choices between a smaller sooner reward and a larger later one, if subjects are induced to image the reward in the low-construal mode, they prefer the smaller sooner one; if they are induced to imagine the reward in the high-construal mode, they prefer the later larger one (Metcalf and Mischel 1999).

vividness of a mental simulation also intensifies an individual's emotional response to a situation,⁵ as people with higher mental imagery tend to experience emotions more intensely (Carroll, Baker, and Preston 1979; Smith and Over 1987; White 1978). The vividness of a simulation makes the pre-experience more realistic, and thus reduces the gap between the individual's pre-experience of an event and the real experience of a similar event, which in turn reduces the individual's hot/cold empathy gap.

We have shown the limitations of mental simulation which prospective mothers are subject to when making moral or practical prenatal decisions. We have also shown how this results in poor forecasting of the intensity and duration of future states, and the construction of unrepresentative and abstract simulations of future selves and events, thus increasing the psychological distance between an individual and their future self. In the next two sections, we will describe the characteristics of VR that reduce the limitations of mental simulations, and examine how VR can be used to aid prospective mothers in making moral and practical prenatal decisions.

5. VR and its potential as a decision-aid in moral and pragmatic prenatal decisions

5.1 Present VR technology and its uses

Virtual reality is a cutting-edge technology. Its present iteration requires the use of a headset that allows the user to enter an immersive visual experience. 3D modelling software can be used to create and represent the salient aspects of an environment in the virtual world and allows interactive components to be built into the landscape. Alternatively, a virtual version of the real world can be used by recording it with 3D stereoscopic cameras.

Advances in VR technology combine visual immersion with other forms of input and output by combining electromagnetic, mechanical and/or optical tracking systems to allow spatial awareness through dynamic audio mapping and equalization. Tracking devices are one of the main components of the VR system and facilitate sophisticated forms of interaction with the virtual environment which are

⁵ Individuals need that their choices are accompanied by an emotional coloring, as emotions carry information; in their absence, the individual could rely only on logic operations connecting alternatives and outcomes and comparing the results (Loewenstein and Lerner 2003b). Not by chance, subjects that are lesioned in the brain area responsible for emotion processing and attribution of value to choice options (ventromedial prefrontal cortex) have troubles in making even the most trivial choices, even though they can compare the choice alternative and forecast their consequences (Damasio 1994; 1996).

made to feel natural to the user. As a result, learning to use a VR interface is notably easier than that of virtual environments experienced through more common input and output systems, such as a keyboard and monitor. The user can use real-world movements, such as walking, touching, and grabbing, to explore and interact with different parts of the virtual environment while simultaneously receiving consistent visual and auditory feedback, such as visual perspective and echolocation. Utilizing a combination of input and output systems gives the VR-user an authentic perception of true reality in a VR scenario.

The immersivity of VR differentiates it from other related technologies such as augmented reality and mixed reality, which instead superimpose a virtual layer of information or simulated objects on a real-world environment. The wholly virtual VR environment prevents a break in the users' state of immersion and facilitates an impression of real presence. The ability of VR to create powerfully immersive simulations and generate deep emotional responses is evident in its success as a medium of exposure therapy for the treatment of phobias (Botella et al. 2017).

VR has been successfully used in a wide range of fields, including the entertainment industry, automotive industry, aviation and aerospace industries, defence industry, architecture and engineering, and medicine and healthcare (Fisher 1991). In many of these fields, VR has been used to develop transferable skills to improve the user's performance in complex real-world contexts. This includes training technical skills, for example in training surgeons to perform laparoscopic surgeries competently (Larsen et al. 2009), and non-technical skills, for example, the situational awareness, communication and decision-making skills necessary in battlefield medicine training or disaster response training (Stansfield, Shawver, and Sobel 1998). Apart from realism and immersivity, VR applications have two further characteristics that are desirable as a tool to support decision-making. Firstly, VR allows users to experience multiple scenarios within a short span of time. Secondly, VR allows each scenario to be explored in depth in a non-linear timeline, allowing participants to withdraw from the simulation if the simulation becomes emotionally overwhelming, and re-entering it at a later time. This allows users to revisit challenging decisional points and safely explore the effect of making different decisions within the simulation, subsequently contextualizing this to their own personal situation.

Alexander Skulmowski and colleagues created a VR scenario depicting the well-known philosophical problem known as the 'trolley dilemma', in which the user has to make a quick moral and social judgement, choosing between a three-to-one and ten-to-one sacrificing scenario. The VR version of the trolley dilemma was created to examine the situational and emotional aspects of moral decision-making that cannot be measured when participants are given the conventional written vignette of this ethical dilemma. In the VR simulated version, participants 'drove' the trolley and had to actively decide which track to direct it to, and consequently, who and how many people would die. The study reproduced existing results, thus validating the new methods used. At the same time, the use of VR allowed physiological measurements, such as pupillometric measurements and the direction of gaze, to be

measured. This provided researchers with information about the dynamics and intensity of the users' emotional response as the scenario unfolded in real-time and enabled them to identify significant moments in the decision-making process. (Skulmowski et al. 2014).

5.2. Implementation of VR as a decision-aid in medical decision-making

We have outlined VR technology and its uses. We would now like to outline some practical considerations on the use of VR in medical decisions that cannot be made only by employing rational choice theory.

5.2.1 Technology-based considerations

There is a wide range of VR technology available, from simple viewers that transform mobile phones into virtual reality headsets, to more sophisticated tethered headsets purpose-built for VR. The technology used should be guided by patient preference, cost, and logistical considerations. Mobile-based headsets are an affordable way of integrating VR into the clinical setting and allow the patient unlimited interaction time with the scenarios. This gives them the time and space to explore, reflect and come back to scenarios of interest before discussing them with their healthcare team. A tethered headset in a dedicated empty room within the clinic is costlier and restricts the engagement time per person. However, its use of more sophisticated technology allows for a more complex and immersive interactive experience. It also enables the monitoring of physiological parameters, which can be a useful tool in the subsequent debrief with healthcare providers.

5.2.2 Healthcare-based considerations

VR use would require additional staff training and a restructuring of certain processes within the healthcare system. For the technology to run smoothly, we suggest that at least one member of staff is dedicated and trained to be familiar with the use of VR technology. This staff member would be able to provide basic technological support to users of the VR system. The use of VR technology is similar to the use of a computer and would not require specialist knowledge in information technology. As such, this task can be performed by any willing member of staff and no additional manpower would need to be hired.

The VR encounter itself would need to be integrated into the present clinical process, and ideally followed soon after by a debrief. We suggest that parents be given autonomy on whether to participate in using VR technology as part of their decision-making process and on choosing the scenarios they wish to

explore. They should also be permitted to exit the scenarios and withdraw from the VR experience at any time if it makes them uncomfortable. We further suggest that the use of VR be complemented by a psychologist or specially trained nurse, who would provide post-VR debriefing support. In this way, participant's reflections, experiences and emotions related to the VR scenario can be explored.

Biopsychosocial support for prenatal decisions has previously been advocated in the literature (McCoyd 2008), although little attention has been paid to operationalizing it in practice. The implementation of virtual reality as a decision-support tool may complement and facilitate this much needed improvement in care strategies to support women and couples through this complex experience. Physiological monitoring during the VR experience could be a way of actively directing this counselling, for example by inviting participants to relate what they felt at points of the VR scenario when their physiological parameters changed. This debriefing process is aimed at actively helping participants elucidate their own needs and preferences. While virtual reality has the potential to overcome the limits of mental simulation, the simulated experience needs to be processed and individually integrated for it to be an effective tool. This would then be followed by the formal medical encounter with their medical doctor. We advise that the use of VR not remove individualized counselling by trained medical professionals, although it may improve scientific communication and fill in service gaps where information transfer is insufficient.

5.3 Ethical issues raised by the use of VR in medical decision-making

Using VR technologies as decision support tools raises ethical concerns that need to be addressed before the development and prototyping phase. Firstly, exposure to a simulated experience may have significant unintended consequences. Reflection on the effects of a simulated experience is not new. In his *Poetics* (Aristotle, n.d., pt. 1448b), Aristotle writes that although exposure to simulated experiences might be useful as a tool for learning, it has the potential to elicit negative emotions such as pity and fear. At the same time, simulated experiences may help the user to achieve freedom from these negative associations. The efficacy of the use of VR in exposure therapy (Botella et al. 2017) illustrates how these virtual scenarios can elicit powerful emotions. Depending on the circumstances, the effects of these emotions can be harmful to people in their actual reality. This needs to be kept in mind in order to minimize any possible psychological harm to users.

Another issue that may arise is the issue of mental privacy (Farah et al. 2008). Studies collecting physiological data during a VR simulation (Skulmowski et al. 2014) prove that it is possible to subtly collect a wealth of physiological data which can then be related to mental functioning during the simulation.

A further ethical concern relates to the cost and accessibility of these systems. Even though VR technology is becoming progressively more affordable, it continues to be priced prohibitively for a large segment of the population. This is one reason why VR technology used to facilitate the provision of healthcare should be released publicly and covered by national health systems or national insurance schemes as opposed to operate via a business-to-consumer model. Apart from ensuring just distribution, accessing the VR tool through the healthcare systems serves another important purpose – it ensures users are briefed before and after the experience, facilitating the discussion of their experience with a trained expert. Projecting oneself into the future can be an intense experience, and contextualizing and reflecting on this experience ex post is useful to distinguish and disentangle the normative and descriptive aspects of the experience. In this way, users are enabled to understand their personal reactions to the simulation, and to collocate them in the context of a well-informed moral reflection.

Lastly, the decision-support tool should make provisions for the involvement of other relevant stakeholders when appropriate, especially since moral and practical prenatal decisions may be relevant to more than just the prospective mother. This could present a challenge with current VR technology. VR simulations are intrinsically solipsistic, allowing only one user at the time. Although multi-user interaction is possible, it requires more complex technology. While single-user simulations can be run using just a headset, a multi-user simulation would require a dedicated empty room equipped with 3D-tracking systems and more powerful computers. As a result, a single-user simulation can be easily run even in the current clinical set-up. On the other hand, simulations inclusive of more than one user are more difficult to arrange from both a logistical and organizational point of view. These concerns need to be taken into account when it is necessary or desirable to involve other stakeholders in the VR experience and subsequent discussions, for example by arranging parallel sessions (with each stakeholder able to individually experience the VR simulation and individually debriefed) before a combined discussion and decision is made.

5.4 VR as a decision-aid in moral and practical prenatal decisions: the enhancement of mental simulation

The ability of VR to be simultaneously realistic yet virtual, and creative yet standardized, supports its use as a decision-support tool when complex mental simulations are necessary. The standardized computer rendering of VR landscapes ensures that immersivity in a scenario is independent of the individual's ability to imagine the scenario, while the flexibility of the creative medium allows multiple vivid scenarios to be explored extensively and evocatively. This overcomes limitations in an individual's ability to mentally simulate future or hypothetical scenarios. The flexibility of the digital medium allows the VR scenario to be as rich as that created by the programmer, with details taken from

reality. This facilitates a low-level construal of the scenario, decoupling details from intense emotional associations of an individual user and overcoming the barrier of essentialising elements of the experience. At the same time, the emotional response triggered by this immersive VR experience provides an important source of information and bridges the empathy gap between the current and prospective future self. The VR scenarios can also be scripted to allow users to explore multiple probabilities as variations of a given experience, depending on the user's choices along decisional points. This enables a user to experience multiple plausible outcomes of a given choice, developing useful insights on the utility of the available options to their personal contexts and in relation to their own moral values. In addition, the events unfolding during a simulation can be coded to be as complete and systematic as possible, thus representing parts of these events that are frequently overlooked in mental simulations. This reduces the impact bias of the mental simulation.

The summative effect of a well-coded immersive VR experience is the facilitation of low construal level representations of the future self, narrowing the psychological distance such that the individual using the VR tool “becomes” her future self in the VR simulation.

6. Employing VR as a decision-aid in moral and practical prenatal decisions: the case of prenatal testing

We have demonstrated the high potential of VR to reduce the inherent biases present in mental stimulations. In spite of this, VR technology has been overlooked as a decision-support tool for patients in the field of medical decision-making. A recent study examining the actual decision-support needs of mothers who had experienced a peri-viable delivery, a particularly sensitive situation fraught with moral and practical prenatal decisions (for example, decisions about infant resuscitation and modes of delivery respectively), showed that mothers valued the availability of a decision-support tool with accurate information that also allowed them to be confronted by the moral implications of their choices. The study concluded that an instrument able to provide emotional context in the form of diachronically structured experiences could improve the relatability of the information and its potential impact (Tucker Edmonds et al. 2019). The characteristic of a decision-support tool most valued by participants was interactivity. For this reason, they perceived a tablet application preferable to a passive VR scenario. The VR scenario proposed in the study was not interactive, and involved a 3D video of neonatal resuscitation, the neonatal intensive care unit, and of life in the years following a peri-viable birth. A passive 3D rendering of a scenario does not leverage on the strengths of VR technology as outlined above. In actuality, the appropriate use of VR technology, with vivid and interactive scenarios, fulfils the brief outlined by participants. In addition, the use of VR brings a degree of relatability, emotional engagement, and immersivity that supersedes the capabilities of a tablet device.

For illustrative purposes, we endeavour to describe the application of VR as a decision-making tool in decisions related to non-invasive prenatal testing (NIPT), although the benefits of VR as a decision-making tool is not limited to this single domain within pregnancy.

6.1 Prenatal testing as a moral and practical prenatal decision

NIPT is a safe and relatively painless method to access the genetic information of an unborn child and provides a high level of sensitivity and specificity. NIPT detects fragments of DNA from apoptosed placental cells that circulate in the maternal circulation. These fragments are extracted from maternal plasma and used as a proxy to assess foetal genetic material (Y. M. D. Lo et al. 1997; 1999). In this way, NIPT requires only a single blood test from the pregnant mother and provides more accurate information for the conditions tested for than other available screening methods. Previous methods of foetal genetic analysis, while diagnostic, required a direct sampling of the chorionic villi or amniotic fluid. This posed procedural risks to the pregnancy, including a small risk of miscarriage. In view of these risks, invasive forms of genetic testing were limited to women screened to be at high risk of an affected child. The safety of NIPT has increased the accessibility of genetic testing to include all pregnant women.

NIPT aims to increase reproductive autonomy by providing information about the genetic and health status of the child. The decision to undergo NIPT is both a moral and practical prenatal decision. The moral values at stake are the woman's reproductive autonomy, the foetus' right to come into existence and – in case a congenital abnormality is detected – the future child's disability rights. This decision is also a practical prenatal one as it involves weighing two contrasting attitudes towards life. One is the mother's (or parent's) need to reduce her uncertainty about the foetus' health condition, which is related to the need to control factors of pregnancy that are difficult to monitor. The other is the acknowledgement and acceptance that not everything can or should be controlled during pregnancy, a concept captured in the term '*openness to the unbidden*' (Sandel 2007).

Ideally, genetic counselling should be provided by a geneticist or genetic counsellor prior to considering genetic screening or testing. This is particularly important with the high sensitivity and specificity of NIPT, on which decisions about whether to keep or terminate a pregnancy may be made. Decision-making becomes particularly difficult when considering complex and late-onset health conditions, and disorders with variable expressivity. However, the absence of therapeutic intervention for the conditions detected limits women to either prepare for a child with a disability or terminate the pregnancy. Although official recommendations state that a positive NIPT result should be confirmed with a diagnostic test before decisions about an abortion are made (Dondorp et al. 2015; Audibert et al. 2017), it is postulated that a significant number of women may act upon their NIPT screening results alone, with

up to 25% of women declining invasive tests regardless of their risk status (Allyse et al. 2012; Dar et al. 2014).

Practically, limited access to genetic counsellors means that counselling is usually performed by the attending obstetrician, who may not be equipped to have these conversations (Mayes et al. 2016). However, even when parents are able to consult genetic counsellors, they may not receive the information they value. Genetic counsellors tend to prioritize the provision of clinical information, while parents' value contextualized information about their child's ability to function in society (Sheets et al. 2011). Parents are often similarly concerned about the impact of the child's disability on their lives and that of other family members, as well as their own ability to cope with caring for a child with disabilities. To humanize people with disabilities and provide a perspective beyond the clinical and medicalized manner in which disability is presented, it has been suggested that prospective parents meet with others who have lived with the disability in question and their families. However, this would not be practicable in reality because of the large scale of prenatal testing with NIPT and may be offensive to people with disabilities by putting them on display.

6.2 The benefits of using VR in prenatal testing decisions

VR can support decisions related to NIPT in two ways. Firstly, virtual reality is a sensitive way of filling the gap in access to genetic counselling services and in the information that prospective parents look for. It enables us to go beyond the provision of a technology-based solution to a logistical limitation and enhancing it instead by providing an immersive, contextualized experience that conventional genetic counselling is unable to provide. Secondly, VR value-adds to the decision-making experience by facilitating a less biased mental simulation.

A recent study on pregnancy and prenatal testing experiences revealed that the large majority of women interviewed referred to beliefs about their presumed behaviour when faced with a foetal anomaly in their pregnancy as hypothetical, and alluded to their uncertainty about how they would react in reality when confronted with an actual decision (Tyebally Fang et. al., unpublished data). In acknowledging their uncertainty and the hypotheticality of their actions, these mothers were in turn acknowledging the psychological distance between their present selves – for whom this decision is relatively abstract – and their future selves. An immersive and evocative virtual reality simulation may be able to shorten this psychological distance, allowing a more honest personal reflection of the reciprocal relations of individual, interpersonal and societal factors. In this way, parents are able to make a better appraisal of their possible future as a parent of a child with a disability.

6.3 Practical recommendations for developing a VR decision-aid suitable for prenatal testing decisions

The use of VR is an opportunity to enhance the clinical encounter, filling in knowledge gaps and presenting complex information in more understandable forms. In the case of prenatal decisions, this requires the developer of the tool to understand these gaps from the parent's perspectives, and to integrate these into the tool. To be able to bridge effectively between hypotheticality and the reality or future reality of a person, scenarios should be based in reality and should facilitate the process of contextualization to the individual's particular circumstances. Rigorous qualitative research collecting a maximum variation sample (Patton 1990, 169–86) of patient accounts should be considered an essential step in developing the scenario. While the scenario should be purpose-built for a specific issue within prenatal decision-making, the demographic sample of first-hand experiences should be broad so that the individual can simultaneously find scenarios they can relate to and be exposed to differing perspectives. Similarly, scenarios should be developed to be specifically reflective of that particular society. For example, the experience of having a child with a disability in Norway would be vastly different from that in Brazil, since the two countries would be expected to have different community values, healthcare systems, and types of social support for disabled children and their families. Two different VR-scapes need to be developed to be relevant to members of these two different societies.

Care needs to be taken to create the virtual worlds related to prenatal testing decisions in as balanced a manner as possible. The virtual world should not simply replicate the medicalized messaging of the clinical encounter but provide a realistic sampling of life with a child with a genetic syndrome with regards to both medical and non-medical aspects. The simulation should be neither overly positive or overly negative, but an attentive and authentic experience. The responsible depiction of life with a prospective child is crucial, as the simulation can be expected to trigger a range of emotional responses which may influence the parent's decisions, including that of whether to continue a pregnancy.

The development of the virtual reality simulation requires an understanding of the ins and outs of life both from the perspective of parents, family members, and children with these syndromes from a wide range of backgrounds relevant to the patient profile of the prenatal clinic providing NIPT. It should consider the specific informational needs of prospective parents, especially that which is unmet by current counselling methods. The virtual reality models should then be built in consultation with stakeholders (both prospective parents, parents of children with disabilities and people with disabilities themselves), and with guidance from social workers, therapists, special education teachers, clinicians, support groups and disability scholars.

Following the VR experience, a skilled nurse practitioner or psychologist could help the woman or couple through a guided reflection of their simulation experience, and answer questions raised by the

experience. The woman or couple would then schedule to meet with their healthcare provider to discuss and decide on their care plan.

6.4 An example of VR scenarios in clinical practice for prenatal testing decisions

A practical and cost-effective way of utilizing VR as a decision-aid for NIPT is at the point of deciding whether or not to undergo the test. VR technology could be used to fill service exigencies in genetic counselling - a prerequisite to informed consent for NIPT - by relaying the relevant data accessibly through interactive audio-visual formats (for example, by providing immersive portrayals of life with children both with and without disabilities, which parents need to understand prior to testing). The VR simulation should facilitate an exploration of the range of possible severities of the syndromes/disabilities being tested for. For example, parents could choose to enter a virtual world where 'their child' with Down Syndrome has a mild degree of mental retardation, and then enter a similar world this time with a child who has a moderate or severe degree of mental retardation, or where they have a neurotypical child with no mental retardation at all. In this way, the medicalized concept of 'mental retardation' common among children with Down Syndrome is brought to life for prospective parents. Virtual reality allows the concept of mental retardation to be experienced as part of the larger whole of the individual child, rather than be the defining feature of the child as is often the case in a medical encounter where the focus is on relaying knowledge about the disability. The virtual child may have a mild developmental delay *and* be a mischievous baby who loves cuddles and her milk bottle. This helps prospective parents evaluate their expectations in context and make a more accurate assessment of its acceptability to them.

The virtual reality simulation could also allow parents to travel forward in time, so that they may be able to experience life with a child with a disability when they are both older. This relates to a concern that many parents have, where they are confident about caring for a child with a disability while healthy and economically active but worry about the child's future when they are older, debilitated or have passed on. To contextualize this information more closely to a parent's particular context, parents may be given the option to recreate their current situation as closely as possible in the virtual world, for example by choosing the size of their 'virtual' family, their living arrangements, and their employment status. In this way, parents not only receive information on what constitutes the genetic syndromes being tested for, but are able to see the effect it may have on a child, and the potential impact of this child on other significant aspects of their life.

As more sophisticated VR technology becomes more accessible, VR can be used to improve contextualization and better enhance affective forecasting. The immersive portrayal of life with children

with differing needs can be expanded to allow parents to interact with children who have the syndromes tested for via NIPT, rather than be only immersed in their lived experiences. Prospective parents could be 'parents' to their virtual child in a vivid simulation that would enable them to care, interact and grow with their child. Elements in the virtual reality landscape could be programmed to respond as typically as possible for the given situation. For example, the virtual child could react to parental stimuli as a child with the given condition typically would. This would reduce the empathy gap between the parents' current state and their future one in case of a child with a given condition.

Apart from allowing prospective parents to explore what life might be with children with a range of abilities and health conditions, VR can also be used to reinforce important but conceptually complex concepts that are part of routine counselling for NIPT. Interactive simulated scenarios could facilitate understanding of the individual versus population risk for foetal abnormalities (e.g. by immersing the individual in a simulated clinical encounter in which random simulated individual risks are generated that translate into the population risk at an aggregate level), understanding possible test outcomes via simulated scenarios (i.e. what does a high risk and low risk test result translate to for a particular individual), and preparing a parent for the processes that might follow so that they are not caught off-

guard when faced with difficult decisions (e.g. the possibility of needing an invasive test and having to actively consider whether to continue with the pregnancy) (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Example of the complete NIPT process, highlighting possible outcomes and active decisions to be considered.

The simulation may integrate experiences from women who have undergone testing (e.g. what they wished they had known/learnt from this experience) to provide prospective parents different perspectives before making their decision. Parents may choose to experience the scenarios most relevant to them, and can then meet with their healthcare provider to clarify their knowledge of testing and testing

procedures, their personal preferences, and to make a decision about whether prenatal testing is acceptable to them.

7. Conclusion

In this contribution, we have defined and outlined the three types of decisions involved in decision-making during pregnancy, which are ordinary, moral, and practical prenatal decisions. We contend that moral and practical prenatal decisions are challenging decisions to make because they involve conflicts among moral values and between moral and non-moral values respectively, and because pregnancy is a transformative experience that fundamentally alters the individual's moral and practical identity from which the above-mentioned values are derived from.

We have shown that rational choice theory cannot adequately support individuals in making moral and practical prenatal decisions firstly because people usually do not exchange non-instrumental goods such as moral values for instrumental goods; secondly, because the transformative nature of pregnancy and parenthood make it difficult to assign utility to the available options; and thirdly, because rational choice theory overestimates the individual's ability to compute probability.

We then explored mental simulation – one of the main processes employed when faced with unfamiliar and novel choices such as moral and practical prenatal decisions – and the biases associated with it in detail. The limitations of mental simulation include poor affective forecasting of imagined events, the empathy gap between the individual's current and imagined state, envisioning an unrepresentative, essentialized and time-limited event, and finally representing one's future self in an abstract manner (i.e. high-level construal), which inclines individuals to treat their future selves as separate from their present selves. These biases of mental simulation may cause individuals to make ill-considered decisions when making moral and practical prenatal decisions.

We have shown how VR can support prospective parents in making moral and practical prenatal decisions by minimizing these biases of mental simulation. It does this by providing parents with immersive vivid, concrete (i.e. low-construal), and authentic representations of possible scenarios. By eliciting a personal reaction to the virtual scenario that is as close as possible

to the actual reaction when in a similar real-world situation, VR facilitates bridging the empathy gap between the individual's current and imagined future self. Another benefit of using VR as a decision-making tool that we have explored is aiding parents in contextualizing the available options to their personal situations by allowing them to explore the likely consequences of a series of choices they might make, as well as their alternatives. In this way, users are able to experience multiple scenarios within a short span of time. This enables them to mentally simulate alternative courses of action and helps them contextualize and choose options most suitable to their moral and practical identities. We have discussed how the simulated experiences may be emotionally intense, and how the use of VR prevents prospective parents from being overwhelmed by their emotions by allowing them to withdraw from and re-enter scenarios when they are ready. At the same time, we suggest care be taken so that exposure to challenging experiences using VR does not cause lasting psychological harm to individual participants. We have suggested a post-VR debrief to deconstruct the VR experience. We recommend this debrief be conducted by a trained professional to guide the individual in understanding their personal values and relating them to the decision under consideration prior to making the actual decision with their healthcare provider.

In developing the VR tool to facilitate decision-making, we have emphasized the need to ensure the possible scenarios are presented in a balanced manner. The tool should consider the specific needs of their target audience and the scenarios based in reality. The VR scenarios that are part of this tool should be community specific. We strongly suggest the VR tool be distributed as part of a public health program rather than a private enterprise for reasons of fairness. Lastly, as moral and practical prenatal decisions may involve and affect more than one person, we suggest identifying and engaging the relevant stakeholders where possible so that a well-considered decision can be made.

We have illustrated how a VR decision-aid tool should be designed in practice through the example of a VR decision-making support for decisions related to NIPT. We have shown how the use of VR in NIPT is able to convey experiential information that may not otherwise be available to an individual, such as the lived experience of a parent with a child with disabilities, which few people have real experience with.

In conclusion, VR can be a powerful tool to help individuals making complex, unfamiliar, and relatively novel decisions such as moral and practical prenatal ones by enhancing their mental simulation, conveying information that may otherwise evade an individual, engaging an

individual's values, roles, and emotions, and operationalizing psychosocial support in the clinical setting.

Contributions of the authors

M. Tyebally Fang conceived the conceptual idea based on her empirical work, which was then further developed together with E. Vigano and G. Spitale.

The following sections were written by MTF: 1, 3, 5.2, 5.4, 6, and 7.

The following sections were written by EV: 2 and 4.

The following sections were written by GS: 5.1, 5.3, and 5.4.

Figure 1 was developed by MTF and GS.

EV analytically restructured the manuscript throughout the drafting process to ensure congruency and integration between interdisciplinary topics. All authors contributed important intellectual content and critically revised, read and approved the final the manuscript.

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